
Guidelines for the implementation of scientific publishing policies of research data citation in scientific publications and assuring access to primary data, used in publications

Version 3.1

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Research Data Alliance Node Slovenia

The Slovenian Social Science Data Archives (ADP) coordinates the activities of the regional node of the Research Data Alliance (RDA),¹ which was established within the European network of regional nodes (supported by the RDA EU 4.0 project) in February 2019. The Node acts as a contact point between the global RDA and the national research community, supports the activities of the Action Plan for Open Science,² and strengthens the culture of data sharing.

RDA is an international, volunteer, member-based organisation focused on developing infrastructure and community activities that reduce barriers to data exchange and sharing, and accelerate data innovation worldwide.

RDA's work is carried out by volunteer groups comprising researchers, ICT experts, research support staff, librarians, and others. Interest groups serve as long-term platforms for communication and coordination, addressing broader topics. Working groups tackle particular issues to implement recommendations, standards, best practices, technical specifications, and tools within a limited timeframe. Their outputs must be immediately available for implementation and use. Before an output is endorsed as an RDA recommendation, it is reviewed by the RDA community. These Guidelines are based on several endorsed outputs from RDA's interest and working groups.

Purpose of the document

One of the goals of RDA Node Slovenia is to support editors and publishers in preparing and implementing **scientific publishing policies for citing research data in scientific publications and providing access to the primary data on which scientific discussions are based.**

The Node's working group has prepared **guidelines** that scientific publishers and editors can use as a starting point for a custom policy for their authors, reviewers, and editors. We thank the working group of the RDA Node Slovenia and other contributors for their comments and suggestions.

The working group is part of the activity of the Action plan for Open Science nr. 6.2.3/3.5: Support for the operation of the RDA Node Slovenia.

¹ Webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-slovenia>.

² Action plan for Open Science for the implementation of Objective 6.2: Open Science to improve the research quality, efficiency, and responsiveness of the Resolution on the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy 2030: <https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MVZI/Znanost/Nacionalne-strategije-in-dokumenti/2023-Action-Plan-Open-Science-Slovenia.pdf>.

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1. Introduction: Open access to research data

The requirements of public science funders, as defined in the Decree on the implementation of scientific research work in accordance with the principles of open science,³ oblige researchers to ensure the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data and other research results (i.e., manage them in accordance with FAIR principles). Researchers must also provide open access to data and other results essential for replication or reuse in other research, following the principle that research results are "as open as possible, as closed as necessary." According to the decree, scientific journals co-financed from public sources by at least 50% must **publish research data curation rules related to research data within scientific articles, as well as information on the accessibility of data analysis tools and other research results, and require their citation in the lists of sources at the end of scientific articles** (Article 4, paragraph 6).

Several articles of the Decree directly regulate the procedures of researchers and scientific journal editors when publishing and citing data.

- **Where to deposit research data** (Article 5, paragraphs 2 and 3):

(2) Research data and other research results shall be deposited in trusted repositories for research data or other research results as soon as feasible, preferably in national or international domain-specific data centres. If these are not accessible for a specific scientific field, research data and other research results may be stored and made openly accessible in trusted multipurpose repositories.

(3) The criteria for identifying trusted repositories for research data, other research results, and multipurpose repositories shall be defined by ARIS, taking into account common solutions in the European Research Area (e.g. in the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation).

- **Data and metadata** (Article 5, paragraph 4):

Research data and other research results must be accompanied by metadata, including information on the tools and instruments required for research data validation and reuse. When designing metadata, research providers must consider the specifics of scientific fields.

- **Deadline for ensuring access to research data** (Article 5, paragraph 1):

Research data and other research results supporting a scientific publication, except in the case of justified exceptions referred to in paragraph three of the preceding Article, shall be made openly accessible no later than the publication of the scientific publication, in which a permanent access point identifier or persistent identifier (hereinafter: PID) shall be cited.

³ Decree on the implementation of scientific research work in accordance with the principles of open science, <https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MVZI/Znanost/Obzorje-Evropa/Novice/2023-Open-Science/Decree-on-the-implementation-of-scientific-research-work-open-science.pdf>. A further explanation is available in Slovenian (Obrazložitev vsebinskih rešitev uredbe o izvajanju znanstvenoraziskovalnega dela v skladu z načeli odprte znanosti, <https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MVZI/Znanost/Dokumenti/Uredba-o-odprti-znanosti-obrazlozitev-clenov-25-10-2023.pdf>).

- **Exceptions to the sharing** of research data under the open access (Article 4, paragraphs 3 and 4):

(3) Exceptions to fully open access to research data and other research results are permitted in justified cases where fully open access is prevented by the protection of intellectual property, personal data, the security of individuals or the state, or other legal constraints. The justification for the exception must be explained in the Data Management Plan (DMP).

(4) In the case of justified exceptions referred to in the preceding paragraph, research data and other research results shall, where possible, be made openly accessible in anonymised or controlled restricted form.

Publication of metadata in cases where research data cannot be shared (Article 4, paragraph 5): *Where research data and other research results cannot be made openly accessible due to the justified exceptions referred to in paragraph three of this Article, and there are no legal constraints preventing the associated metadata from being openly accessible, at least the metadata shall be made openly accessible.*

- **Use of licenses** (Article 7, paragraphs 3 and 5):

(3) Where copyright, related rights or other rights of the author arise in research data and other research results (such as research software or research methods), the authors or their employers shall, if the copyright is vested in them by law, publish these under an open licence that allows anyone to freely use, modify and share the research data and other research results in accordance with the principles of scientific research ethics (for example, the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) and Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike (CC BY-SA) licences, or their equivalents).

(5) Metadata of research data and other research results shall be made publicly available in accordance with the requirements set out in Article 4 of this Decree. If the metadata of research data and other research results give rise to copyright, related rights or other rights of the author under the law governing copyright and related rights, the metadata shall be made available under a licence by which the authors waive their copyright, related rights and other rights as authors to the fullest extent permitted by law (for example, the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) licence, or, where this is not possible, under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence).

- **Alignment with European Research Area practices** (Article 4, paragraph 7):

The rules of funders, public research organisations, and publicly co-financed scientific journals established in the Republic of Slovenia regarding the handling of research data shall comply with the recommended practices of the European Research Area.

The provisions of the Decree apply to both research data and other research results, with the Decree mentioning software and other types of results in digital form. Although the recommendations below focus on research data, they may also be considered when developing guidelines for managing other research results, depending on the specific nature of the field covered by the journal. When developing guidelines for authors, special attention should be paid to the definition of research data, and the explanation of the content, formats, and forms of research data should be adapted to the scientific field of the journal.

2. Guidelines and instructions for storing and citing research data accompanying the publication

Below, we link the provisions of the Decree with the recommendations of the RDA working groups and other relevant sources. The guidelines and draft instructions for preparing scientific journal policies in Slovenia are based primarily on a review of journal policies worldwide, prepared by a Research Data Policy Interest Group.⁴ In doing so, we follow established recommendations regarding the citation of research data.^{5, 6} Our general definitions of research data and guidelines on the location of deposition and access to research data are based on the Decree.

The guidelines are followed by examples of instructions for authors, which editors may adapt to the field and citation style of their journal as needed. For some elements, editors can decide whether to make certain requirements mandatory or recommend them as guidelines.

2.1 Research data definition

Research data are (digitally readable) records of facts⁷, obtained by various methods, which serve to learn, test, or confirm hypotheses and to implement and present findings.⁸ The integrity of the data underlying the findings presented in the publication enables transparency and verifiability of processing and use, as well as usability for further analysis. Research data may include raw or processed digital or analogue records with associated metadata, numerical values, text, image or audio records, protocols, analytical codes, and workflows.⁹ Regardless of whether the authors collected the primary data themselves or used secondary data, they must cite both appropriately in the article and indicate where they are available for reuse.

The content, recording formats, and formats of research data depend on the research subject and methodological procedures. Editorial boards should adopt a definition of research data that is broad and inclusive, yet specific enough to capture the field's characteristics in terms of methodology, research content, formats, and legal particularities.

Scientific publications should be accompanied by metadata and other information necessary to understand the research data on which the authors based their findings, as well as information on where

⁴ Research Data Policy IG, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/research-data-policy-ig/>. See also Hrynaszkiewicz, I., Simons, N., Hussain, A., Grant, R. and Goudie, S. (2020). Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers. *Data Science Journal*, 19(1). <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-005>.

⁵ Martone, M. (ur.). (2014). *Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles*. FORCE11. <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egyk>.

⁶ CESSDA Data Citation Guide, <https://datacitation.cessda.eu/>, or Bornatici, C., Jernung, A., Alaterä, T. J., Tveit Sandberg, L., Strand, K., Štebe, J., & Trtíková, I. (2025). *CESSDA Recommendations on Data Citation: Practical Recommendations for Key Stakeholders*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15043854>, which contains a special chapter presenting recommendations for citing data and accompanying materials for journals and publishers.

⁷ *National strategy of open access to scientific publications and research data in Slovenia 2015-2020*, 2015, <https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MIZS/Dokumenti/ZNANOST/Strategije/National-strategy-of-open-access-to-scientific-publications-and-research-data-in-Slovenia-2015-2020.pdf>, p. 15.

⁸ *Dictionary of Open Science*, <https://terminoloski.slovenscina.eu/termin/39057>.

⁹ *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>.

these data are accessible. The data should be as comprehensive, detailed, and complete as possible, including unpublished or unused parts of the collected data. They should also include all additional materials and tools that facilitate the reproduction and understanding of the published analyses.

Guidelines:

- Instructions for authors should include a definition of research data.
- They should include examples of data types and formats.
- The editorial board should establish the requirements for data integrity (complete data sets that enable further analysis), documentation of data processing, and traceability of data use in the publication.

Example of instructions to authors:

Research data are obtained by various methods to learn, test, or confirm hypotheses and to derive and present findings. Data may be visual, textual, numerical, and so on. They should also include metadata and any additional materials and tools that help reproduce and understand the published analyses.

The research data used in the publication must be accessible as a data publication¹⁰ in the form of an intact data set, even if only certain parts of the data or selected variables are cited in the scientific publication. Authors must provide information on where these data are accessible.

2.2 Where and how to publish data

Authors must ensure that the primary data are available in a domain-specific data repository when submitting an article for review to the editorial board, or, if this is not possible, in an appropriate institutional or general open access repository. By citing the persistent identifier of the data, a link is established between the data and the publication based on the data used.

In addition to the data, related materials necessary for understanding and confirming the results should be made available, such as documentation of data creation and processing procedures and the corresponding programme code.¹¹ Information on the tools and instruments required to confirm the results (e.g., specialised software or programme code, analysis protocols, etc.) should be published as separate publications, and their use should be ensured in the package for the purpose of replicating the analysis results.¹²

¹⁰ Data publication is a quality-reviewed publication in a data repository that features comprehensively documented data with bibliographical information and persistent identifier (Terminological Dictionary of Open Science, <https://terminoloski.slovenscina.eu/termin/39035>).

¹¹ Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Barker, M., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez, C., Psomopoulos, F. E., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P. A., Honeyman, T., Struck, A., Lee, A., Loewe, A., van Werkhoven, B., Jones, C., Garijo, D., Plomp, E., Genova, F., ... RDA FAIR4RS WG. (2022). FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>.

¹² See also CESSDA Recommendation 4 for journals and publishers, <https://datacitation.cessda.eu/Recommendations-for-Journals-and-Publishers>.

Publishing data in a domain-specific data centre is the best way to ensure the integrity and completeness of data documentation for reuse. To comply with the FAIR principles, publicly available metadata should be as comprehensive as possible to enable findability and usability. Metadata should also include a permanent link (e.g. DOI) to the accompanying publication and other data-related research outputs (such as research programmes).

The Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (hereinafter: ARIS) has prepared a list of recommended repositories¹³ for publishing research data, as well as scientific publications and other research outputs. This list is based on mandatory and recommended criteria for trusted repositories, which include, among other things, assigning persistent identifiers to digital objects, providing metadata, information on the type of access, ongoing user support, and ensuring the long-term curation of digital objects.

Editors and authors may suggest adding other repositories to the list. In making the selection, consult the FAIRsharing list,¹⁴ re3data registry¹⁵, Open Research Europe platform recommendations,¹⁶ and RDA guidelines.¹⁷ The repository must meet minimum requirements: review of data suitability and evaluation of data usability, existence of minimum metadata and related searchability, definition of licences and possible access restrictions, funder and project information, and information necessary to understand the origin and content of data for reuse. It is also necessary to check whether the repository ensures long-term curation and access to data and whether metadata will remain accessible even if the data is no longer available.

Guidelines for cooperation and coordination between publishers and repositories are also being prepared by the domain-specific RDA working group.¹⁸

Guidelines:

- In addition to research data, related materials necessary for understanding research results or scientific publications should also be made available.
- Domain-specific data repositories should be recommended as the preferred location for data publication.
- Editors should recommend that authors use the most appropriate repositories for their field from the ARIS list.

Examples of instructions to authors:

In accordance with the [Decree on the implementation of scientific research work based on the principles of open science](#), the co-financier of the journal ([Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency](#)) requires the editorial board to ensure that authors provide open access to the research data used in preparing

¹³ List of recommended repositories (available in Slovenian), <https://www.aris-rs.si/sl/akti/24/inc/Seznam-repozitorijev1.pdf>.

¹⁴ A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies, <https://fairsharing.org/>.

¹⁵ Registry of Research Data Repositories, <https://doi.org/10.17616/R3D>.

¹⁶ Open Research Europe-approved repositories, <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines#approvedrepositories>.

¹⁷ Cannon, M., Graf, C., McNeice, K., Chan, W. M. in dr. (2021). *Repository Features to Help Researchers: An invitation to a dialogue*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4683794>.

¹⁸ Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes Working Group, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/coordinating-earth-space-and-environmental-science-data-preservation-and-scholarly-publication-processes-wg/activity/>.

the article before publication. The data must be prepared in accordance with the [FAIR principles](#) (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability).

Data and related materials should be published in a trusted domain-specific, institutional, or general data repository that allows for appropriate access regimes in cases of justified restrictions (in compliance with the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary"). Domain-specific (national international) data centres recognised by the community are preferred over general repositories. Trusted data repositories recommended by the journal's co-funding body are [listed here](#). After consulting the editorial board, the author may suggest another place of publication.

2.3 Exceptions to data sharing in the open access regime

The decree permits authors to withhold research data from open access for reasons such as intellectual property protection, personal data protection, threats to the safety of individuals or the state (including the environment), or legal restrictions. Exceptions to data sharing are justified in cases involving personal or sensitive data, intellectual property protection, or the protection of endangered areas, groups, or species. In these cases, authors may adapt the published research data by anonymising certain values or, in cooperation with the repository responsible for data publication, restrict access under specific conditions. Research data with restricted access is still considered open research data when its metadata record is published in the repository. If the repository supports double-blind peer review, the data is available to editors and reviewers without revealing authorship before publication.

If the authors and editors decide that the research data cannot be shared at all, the authors must provide access to the metadata of the research results. The metadata should also include information about the reasons for restricting access.

If authors decide to restrict access to data, they may indicate this in the data availability statement (DAS), briefly explain the reasons for data protection, access restrictions, conditions and methods of data access, and describe how they comply with the journal's or funder's data access provisions.

Guidelines:

- The editorial board should define cases where data is not fully open access as exceptions and specify what alternative forms of access are available.
- If, due to the specific nature of the field (e.g. medicine, genetics, ethnography), research data must be made available only to a limited group of researchers or groups, reference should be made to examples and established practice elsewhere when determining permissible exceptions.
- Alternative access options should be offered, such as access to anonymised versions of the data, secure regulated access with predefined access conditions, and the option of accessing metadata only.
- The publication may be accompanied by a data availability statement (DAS), which briefly explains to readers how the author complies with the journal's or funder's data access requirements.

Examples of instructions to authors:

Exceptions to data sharing are justified in cases involving personal or sensitive data, the protection of intellectual property, or the protection of endangered areas, groups, or species. In such cases, data

may be shared in anonymised form or under controlled access conditions. Editors and reviewers must have access to data in agreement with the data archive, including under conditions of anonymised authorship information, if the archive allows double-blind peer review.

Exceptions and special cases regarding access to data should be explained by the author in an accompanying statement on data accessibility and in publicly available metadata when the article is published. The reasons for access restrictions, conditions, and other options for accessing data, as well as the location of the data, should be described. The data accessibility statement should include a reference to the data publication from the list of sources (see data citation). Metadata must be publicly available and accessible, even when the data is not, or is no longer, available.

2.4 Deadlines for data publication and the possibility of embargo

The data must be available to editors and reviewers when the publication is submitted for review, and to all others at the latest upon publication. Embargoes on access to data are not permitted, except in exceptional cases with additional justification.

Researchers are advised to deposit their data in the appropriate repository before submitting their publication for review, in order to obtain a permanent identifier, which forms the basis for citing the data. They should note that the publication process in domain-specific repositories may take longer. Until the article is published, it is possible to withhold the publication of data by agreement with the repository.

Guidelines:

- Research data must be published as soon as possible after its creation (before the first analysis), or at the latest upon publication of the scientific article.
- The editorial board should limit unreasonably long embargo requests.

Examples of instructions to authors:

The data must be available to editors and reviewers when the publication is submitted for review, and to all others no later than upon publication. A limited embargo on data access is permitted in exceptional cases with appropriate additional justification.

2.5 Citing data sources

The author of the publication is required to cite the data in question in the same manner as other sources: within the text, under graphs and tables, and in the list of sources and literature used in the publication. This also applies when the author uses research data from their own research in the publication. Other authors who use data published in the relevant repository should cite the data in accordance with academic standards, regardless of where they publish the results of their analyses, even if the data publication has a CC0 licence. Other Creative Commons licences and similar licences usually already require citation.

Current recommendations (*Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles* FORCE11 in RDA,¹⁹ *The Tromsø Recommendations of the Interest Group Linguistic Data*,²⁰ *Precise, Actionable Reference to Dynamic Data* of Data Citation working group,²¹ *article A data citation roadmap for scientific publishers*,²² COPDESS recommendations,²³ *Data Citation Guidelines for Earth Science Data*,²⁴ and CESSDA recommendations²⁵) advise that bibliographic records of research data should include of at least the following elements:

1. names of author or authors of the research data,
2. full title of the research data,
3. year of publication of the specific version of the research data in the data repository,
4. version,
5. the institution or repository where the data are published,
6. persistent identifier for the data publication (e.g. DOI).

The reference to the data publication may also include the following elements, depending on the characteristics of the data source and the specific domain of the journal:

1. Version: the default value is a single version. The default is "dynamic," meaning the source can change without explicit versions or timestamps; in this case, the access date is also required.
2. Media: the default value is digital format. Specification is required if other digital formats (e.g., CD-audio, CD-ROM text file) or analogue formats (e.g., books, archive files) are used.
3. Date of access to the data source: this should be recorded if the source changes or if there is no guarantee it will remain unchanged.

Authors should follow the citation guidelines of the repository where they published their data and adapt the format to the standard used by the scientific journal. Editors should verify that the author has cited the data appropriately.

Guidelines:

- The author of the publication is obliged to cite the data in question in the same way as other sources in the text and in the list of sources and literature.

¹⁹ Martone, M. (ed.). (2014). *Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles*. FORCE11. <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egyk>.

²⁰ Andreassen, H. N., Berez-Kroeker, A. L., Collister, L., Conzett, P., Cox, C., De Smedt, K., McDonnell, B. and Research Data Alliance Linguistic Data Interest Group. (2019.) *The Tromsø Recommendations for Citation of Research Data in Linguistics*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00040>.

²¹ Rauber, A., Parsons, M., & RDA Data Citation WG. (2025). *Precise, Actionable Reference to Dynamic Data: Recommendations of the Working Group on Data Citation (WGDC) (Version 2)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00132>.

²² Cousijn, H. et al. (2018). A data citation roadmap for scientific publishers. *Sci Data* 5, 180259 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.259>.

²³ COPDESS Suggested Author Instructions and Best Practices for Journals, <https://copdess.org/copdess-suggested-author-instructions-and-best-practices-for-journals/>

²⁴ ESIP Data Preservation and Stewardship Committee, (2019). *Data Citation Guidelines for Earth Science Data*. Ver. 2. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.8441816>.

²⁵ Bornatici, C., Jernung, A., Alaterä, T. J., Tveit Sandberg, L., Strand, K., Štebe, J., & Trtíková, I. (2025). *CESSDA Recommendations on Data Citation: Practical Recommendations for Key Stakeholders (1-0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15043854>. The CESSDA recommendations summarize existing approaches and clearly define the mandatory and optional elements of data citation. The recommendations are furthermore divided into sections specifically for authors, journals and publishers, repositories, and ethics bodies.

- The editorial board should provide examples of how to cite data in accordance with the chosen citation style.
- The journal should alert technical staff, editors and reviewers to the requirement for mandatory citation of data publications.
- Authors should follow the recommendations for citing data from the repository to which they have submitted their data.

Examples of instructions to authors:

When citing research data, the author should include the authors, title, year of publication, version, place of publication (repository), and persistent identifier (e.g. DOI).

Examples of data publication references in [preferred citation style]:

Example of citation in the text: (Hafner - Fink and Malešič, 2016).

Example in the bibliography:

Hafner - Fink, M. and Malešič, M. (2016). Slovene Public Opinion 2015: International survey Work orientation (ISSP 2015), International survey Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of Public Opinion and National Security Survey [Data file]. Ljubljana: University of Ljubljana, Slovenian Social Science Data Archives. https://doi.org/10.17898/ADP_SJM15_V1.

2.6 Licences

The decree requires the use of open access licences such as Creative Commons (of which CC BY or CC0 are generally considered first choice),²⁶ or equivalent licences.²⁷

Guidelines:

- The data is marked with a licence from the set offered by the data repository.
- The journal does not require that the licence over the data be transferred to the journal or publisher.

Examples of instructions to authors:

Data should be openly accessible under Creative Commons licences (CC0, CC BY, CC BY-SA, etc.) or other appropriate licences, such as those available in the data repository where the data are accessible.

²⁶ See <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/ccllicenses/>.

²⁷ Decree, Article 7(3); this paragraph also mentions attribution – sharing under the same conditions (CC BY-SA), which can severely limit the possibilities for reusing research data and is not found in other similar international provisions. In contrast, Creative Commons dedication to the public domain (CC0) is appropriate for research data, as is also required for metadata in paragraph 5 of the aforementioned article of the Decree.

2.7 Support for authors

Authors should follow the recommendations and requirements of the chosen data repository. Assistance with implementing instructions on data publication may be provided by an authorised data centre, institutional repository, library, or domain-specific data stewards on behalf of the publisher. Depending on the specifics of the scientific field, editorial offices should advise authors where to seek support in managing research data.

Guidelines:

- Editors should provide information on whom authors can contact for advice on implementing the instructions.

Examples of instructions to authors:

Authors should follow the recommendations and requirements of the selected data repository. Assistance in implementing the instructions on data publication and access is provided by the [data centre, institutional repository, library]. If you have any questions, please write to [address].

3. Implementation

Depending on the circumstances, the editorial board of the journal may adopt a more or less strict policy on data sharing and adapt the guidelines so that individual provisions, as obligations or recommendations, are included. In doing so, it should consider the framework set out in the Decree.

Editorial offices should prepare a plan to inform and train technical staff and reviewers on enforcing compliance with the citation and data publication instructions.

The FAIRsharing portal can assist in preparing and documenting the final content of a specific policy, using its standardised scheme of elements for labelling policies.²⁸ When preparing the policy, collaboration with the portal also helps identify suitable repositories for data deposit and related standards. The final version of the journal's policy is registered on the portal, together with the relevant standards and repositories. In this way, information about the repositories with which the journal collaborates can be accessed and later edited as needed, for example, when preparing specific instructions for authors.²⁹ The portal also enables the registration and description of the publisher's overarching policy, which can be referenced in the instructions of individual journals within the publisher.³⁰

²⁸ FAIRsharing, <https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/registry-type#policies>.

²⁹ Sansone, SA., McQuilton, P., Rocca-Serra, P. et al. FAIRsharing as a community approach to standards, repositories and policies. *Nat Biotechnol* 37, 358–367 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-019-0080-8> and flyer for publishers: Kay Burrows, Allyson Lister, & Susanna-Assunta Sansone. (2023, July 26). *FAIRsharing for you: journal publishers*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8186640>

³⁰ Registry of publishing policies, https://fairsharing.org/search?fairsharingRegistry=Policy&page=1&recordType=journal_publisher.

Collaboration with repositories is useful for providing information about the procedures and options that individual repositories offer to data authors and editorial offices. For example, as stated in CESSDA Recommendation 6 to journals and publishers for citing data, – it is advisable for journals to inform authors in their instructions that publishing data in trusted repositories involves editorial review and that data must be deposited sufficiently in advance. Some repositories allow access to data for review purposes before public release.³¹ Certain domain-specific research data repositories can advise editorial boards at various stages of developing journal policies and author guidelines.

When developing editorial policy, consideration should be given to the scientific community in the relevant field and established expectations regarding data sharing requirements and other research results.³² In preparing the guidelines, we took into account, as a minimum, the provisions of national policy and the manner of its implementation by ARIS, which co-finances journal publication. We also endeavoured to ensure that the guidelines are consistent with the requirements set for contractors of publicly funded research projects.

Editors may also refer to the general instructions prepared by scientific publishers and RDA Node Slovenia.³³

Various resources on planning research data management are available to authors and editors.³⁴ Editorial offices can also seek advice from the Centre for Quality Assurance in Science Communication³⁵ and from support services at universities.³⁶

4. Conclusion

Scientific publishers and editorial offices can use the guidelines as a working tool when preparing instructions tailored to the specific domain of the journal.

As a living document, they reflect current knowledge and practices. In line with new findings and developments on the matter, the working group of the RDA Node Slovenia will supplement and update them as appropriate.

Any questions or suggestions regarding the content of the document can be addressed to the RDA Node Slovenia (Vozlisce.RDA@fdv.uni-lj.si).

³¹ CESSDA Data Citation Guide, <https://datacitation.cessda.eu/Recommendations-for-Journals-and-Publishers>

³² For considerations regarding policy implementation, see also the analysis of the first phase of policy introduction in Slovenia: Štebe, J., Dolinar, M., Bezjak, S. and Inkret, A. (2020) *Implementing the RDA Research Data Policy Framework in Slovenian Scientific Journals*, *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p. 49. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-049>.

³³ Research data management (Notes for authors), <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jdXmBl9HiQ-gItliH51bjjJ0Z6bm86ue/edit>. An abridged version is also available.

³⁴ The fundamental resource in Slovenian is Bezjak S., Grašič J., Korez B., Kverh B., Leskošek B., Romih T., Vipavc Brvar I., Zagorščak M., Županič A. (2025). *Priročnik o načrtovanju ravnanja z raziskovalnimi podatki*. Ljubljana: Založba Univerze v Ljubljani. <https://doi.org/10.51936/9789612975944>.

³⁵ Contact: <https://odprta-knjiznica.si/kontakt/>.

³⁶ These include a network of data stewards and contact persons to support research data management at the University of Ljubljana (raziskovalni.podatki@uni-lj.si), professional support for open science at the University of Primorska (odprta.znanost@upr.si) and University of Maribor library (odprimo@um.si).